

VISUAL CONNECTIONS

A New Category for a Research Journal

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THE PURPOSE

Visual Connections encourages interdisciplinary dialogue, highlighting the ways in which health science, humanities, and the arts interact.

THE GENESIS

Innovations
Subcommittee
Brainstorming

Spring 2025

Associate Editor
on board

Summer 2025

Category
Launch

Fall 2025

REVIEW CRITERIA

Originality

Relevance

Intellectual
Engagement

Design
Quality

Overall
Presentation

AUTHORS' GUIDELINES

SCOPE

- A brief narrative

CONTENT

- Visual Works
- Poetry/Prose

FORMAT

- .jpg, .docx acceptable
- Anonymized

SUBMISSION

- Optional abstract
- [Example](#)

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SPECIAL THANKS

Margaret Hoogland

Laureen P. Cantwell-Jurkovic

<https://journals.indianapolis.iu.edu/index.php/hypothesis/viscon>